

Design and Simulation of Reliable Desuperheating Methods for a Multi-Stage Oil-Free R718 Compressor for High-Temperature Heat Pumps

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Extended Abstract

Introduction

High-temperature heat pumps (HTHP) are key to support industrial decarbonization, and innovation is under progress to meet demands above 150 °C. Water (R718) is a promising refrigerant for such temperatures. It is totally environmentally friendly, non-toxic, non-flammable, inexpensive [1,2], has high latent heat of vaporization and critical temperature of 374°C, making it convenient for high-temperature applications [1,2]. However, excessive discharge superheat and large compression ratios remain challenges, limiting practical applications [3]. Desuperheating between compression stages is essential to limit operating temperatures in R718 compressors. An established approach towards desuperheating is direct liquid injection, controlling the liquid water stream according to the superheating degree [1,3]. However, this solution may pose risks for some compressor types, such as oil-free reciprocating compressors, especially during transients such as start-up, shut-down, or part-load operation, and alternative approaches may be needed.

This study presents the design and simulation of a desuperheating system developed for a novel oil-free, multi-stage reciprocating compressor using water (R718) as working fluid. The compressor, designed in collaboration with an industrial manufacturer, operates with sub-atmospheric suction and is intended for integration in high-temperature heat pumps (HTHPs) delivering heat at up to 185 °C. Its innovative oil-free design relies on specialized surface coatings in the compression chambers, which are highly sensitive to liquid droplets, imposing constraints to the design of the HTHP and particularly to how desuperheating of the discharged steam is attained.

Methods

The compressor prototype used in this HTHP has a discharge temperature limit of 260 °C according to the manufacturer. Direct liquid injection to provide latent heat for 100% of the desuperheating load between stages was discarded after an initial assessment of scientific and technical documentation due to a potential risk of droplet ingress into the compression chambers. Thus, two two-step desuperheating concepts were explored.

The first concept involves desuperheating the discharge stream from each compressor stage via a dedicated heat exchanger, where high-pressure liquid is entirely evaporated and then merged with the

vapor stream under carefully controlled conditions before entering the next stage (Figure 1, left). The second concept starts desuperheating in a gravity-driven evaporator using high-pressure water from a liquid separator located downstream of the condenser (not represented in the Figure 1 for simplicity). The vapor produced returns to the condenser. Finally, the remaining part of superheat is removed via injection of substantially reduced amount of liquid to meet the required inlet temperature for each stage. Figure 1 right depicts this second desuperheating concept for the 4th stage of compression only but is equivalent for the 3rd and 2nd stages. In all cases and compressor stages, 20 K superheat is the design objective that is set to allow for safety margin with respect to saturation conditions.

Figure 1. Left, HTHP simplified sketch with first desuperheating concept. Right, the second desuperheating concept, focusing on the 4th stage of compression.

Thus, only the superheating of the 1st compression stage remains to be adjusted, since the vapor drawn from the LP DRAIN (see Figure 1) is at saturated conditions and a 20 K superheat is also required here. In the first concept, the necessary heat is provided by bypassing a small portion of the superheated vapor discharged from the 4th compression stage. In the second concept, an electric heater is used, and its power consumption is included in the HTHP efficiency (COP) calculation.

Simulations were performed under steady-state conditions to compare the performance of both concepts and evaluate the compromise between energy efficiency and reliability.

Results and Discussion

Figure 2 compares the heating capacity and COP of the HTHP at different inlet temperatures of the secondary fluid (thermal oil) entering the condenser, and as a function of the desuperheating method applied. Specifically, "First" refers to the initial concept, which uses indirect heat exchange followed by mixing (Figure 1, left), while "Second" corresponds to the alternative concept, which involves gravity-driven flow and injection (Figure 1, right).

The system shows significantly improved performance when the second desuperheating concept is applied. This is because desuperheating in the gravity-driven heat exchanger directly contributes to the heating capacity of the heat pump, since the vapor generated in all the desuperheaters is condensed in the condenser, transferring heat to the thermal oil. Only the portion of desuperheating heat transferred to the injected stream is lost from the perspective of heating the condenser's secondary loop. Under equivalent conditions, the HTHP's heating capacity is 19–26% higher with the second desuperheating concept, while the COP increases by 7–19%. A contribution to these percentages may come from the 1st stage superheating control option, but its individual effect was not assessed separately in this study.

Figure 2. Heating capacity (Q_{cond}) and COP of the heat pump as a function of the thermal oil inlet temperature (secondary fluid in the condenser) and of the type of desuperheating method. Heat source inlet temperature equal to 90 °C in all cases.

Figure 3 illustrates the roles of gravity-driven and injection-based desuperheating, both components of the second desuperheating method proposed in this article, under various operating conditions. Due to the relatively low suction temperature required at the compressor second stage (DESUP1), injection is always necessary, and the fraction handled by the gravity-driven evaporator is lower than in other stages (DESUP2 and DESUP3). In contrast, for the 4th compression stage (DESUP3), the gravity-driven heat exchanger can handle all desuperheating under certain operating conditions, namely up to 160 °C. At 165 °C and above, a small amount of liquid injection may be required. In all cases, the contribution of the gravity-driven heat exchanger (as a percentage of total desuperheating) decreases as the thermal oil inlet temperature increases. This is due to the resulting higher condensing temperature, which limits the effect of the gravity-driven process.

Figure 3. Desuperheating method combining gravity-driven and injection. Left, mass flow injected for desuperheating, per desuperheating level, as a function of thermal oil inlet temperature. Right, percentage of desuperheating heat covered by the gravity-driven heat exchanger, per desuperheating level, as a function of thermal oil inlet temperature.

Figure 4 shows how the maximum discharge temperature determined at the compressor depends on the desuperheating method used, as well as the thermal oil inlet temperature and the heat source inlet temperature (90 °C, 95 °C). The second desuperheating method outperforms the first under identical operating conditions. As the thermal oil inlet temperature increases, the discharge temperature approaches, and in some cases exceeds, the limit specified by the compressor manufacturer (indicated by the black dashed line). This outcome is expected, given the large temperature lift (and corresponding total pressure ratio) achieved with only four compression stages. In practice, this challenge will be addressed by allowing lower superheating degrees (e.g., 15 K) for the 4th and possibly the 3rd compressor stage. Additionally, it is expected that the actual compressor performance, particularly in terms of isentropic efficiency, will be better than what is assumed in the model, which uses a conservative fixed value of 0.775 across all stages and conditions. Also, partial recirculation of the discharge flow from the 4th compression stage is possible to reduce the discharge temperature at the 4th stage, at the expense of certain increase of the temperature in the 3rd stage. This will be evaluated in detail soon.

Figure 4. Maximum discharge temperature registered at the compressor, as a function of the thermal oil inlet temperature and of the type of desuperheating method. Different heat source inlet temperatures are explored (85 °C, 90 °C, 95 °C), as indicated by the legend. The black dashed line represents the maximum temperature allowed according to the compressor manufacturer.

The numerical results obtained in this study demonstrate that the second desuperheating concept enables higher COP and lower discharge temperatures, with the slight risk of a reduced injection of pressurized water. This concept will be designed, assembled, and implemented in a prototype as shown in Figure 5, and will be tested within the context of the same project. From the compressor safety perspective, liquid injection will be controlled according to the superheating degree at each compressor stage using a metering valve, in line with a solenoid valve providing the additional safety level in case undesired conditions are attained, i.e. excessively low superheating degree. Initially, a tube-in-tube injector has been conceptualized, and its capabilities will be validated experimentally.

Figure 5. Preliminary design schematic of prototype thermal system to be tested. Zoomed in area shows preliminary design concept of liquid water injection method that aims to promote water evaporation and minimize the risk of entrained liquid water droplets into the compressor.

Conclusions

This study has demonstrated that two-stage desuperheating, combining gravity-driven evaporation and reduced liquid injection, has a significant potential for improving HTHP performance while keeping the risk of liquid carryover under control. Preliminary simulation results indicate that this approach can increase the HTHP COP by 7 % to 19 % compared to an alternative two-stage desuperheating strategy. The functionality, reliability and effectiveness of this innovative method will be confirmed soon through dynamic simulations, and, subsequently, validated experimentally within a designed and manufactured pilot testing thermal system.

References

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